

THE ROLE AND CLASSIFICATIONS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: In this article is discussed the role and classification of phraseological units, how to classify phraseological units and resources.

Key words: phraseology, phraseological combinations, phraseological unities, phraseological content, idioms

Phraseology is one of the fastest growing fields in the further development of linguistics. While phraseology has been studied in Russian and English linguistics for a long time, it has been systematically in Uzbek linguistics since the 1940s and 1950s. During this period Sh.Rakhmatullayev (1969), G.A.Bayramov (1970), G.H.Akhunzyakov (1974), V.G.Uraksin (1975), L.K.Bayramova (1983), M.F.Chernov (1986) are devoted doctoral dissertations to the study of phraseology. The sources of origin of phraseological combinations in English into three main groups.

1. Old phraseological combinations in English
2. Phraseological combinations learned from other languages
3. Phraseological combinations derived from the American version of English

Phraseology is a science that studies the phraseological layers of each language, their formation, structure and functions. The term phraseology is considered to have two meanings, firstly, it is understood as a set of fixed word combinations in a specific language, that is, phraseologisms, and secondly, it means the branch of the language that studies fixed combinations. As we have seen, the science of phraseology carries out classification, study and research of fixed word combinations that increase the colour of our language.

The most important problem of this section is to distinguish phraseologisms in speech and to determine their signs. The main tasks of phraseology include the following:

- a) determining the consistency of phraseological content;
- b) study the characteristics of phraseology;
- c) describing homonymy, synonymy and paronymy of phraseology;
- d) determining the specific features of the words used in phraseology and their specific meanings;
- e) clarifying the relationship between phraseology and word groups;
- f) determine their syntactic role;
- g) studying the formation of new meanings of words within phraseological units and other similar tasks.

There is a set of classification of phraseological combinations depending on what characteristic sign of phraseological unit is taken as a basis. In this article phraseological units are classified from the point of view of morphological character of their components and a role of components of phraseological units in formation of their semantic structure.

There are three types of phraseological units:

1. Phraseological unions, or idioms are absolutely indivisible, indecomposable steady combinations which general meaning doesn't depend on value of the words making them: **kick the bucket** (spoken)-to be bent, die; **send somebody to Coventry**-to boycott someone, to stop communication with someone; **at bay**-being tired out in a stalemate; to rain cats and dogs-to pour in buckets (about a rain), be all thumbs-to be awkward, clumsy; Kilkenny cats-deadly enemies. Phraseological unions arose on the basis of figurative senses of their components, but subsequently these figurative senses became unclear from the point of view of the modern language. Imagery of phraseological unions reveals only historically. For example, the words "bay", meaning "deadlock", and "beck"- "a hand wave" are archaisms and they aren't used anywhere except the phraseological units given above. The phraseological unit of **Kilkenny cats** (which, apparently, goes back to a legend of fierce between direct and figurative values is lost in phraseological unions, figurative for them became the basic. For this reason it is difficult to translate phraseological unions into other languages.

Phraseological unities are such steady combination of words in which in the presence of the general figurative sense signs of semantic separateness of components distinctly remain; **to spill the beans**-to give out a secret; **to burn bridges**-to destroy one's path, connections, etc., particularly intentionally; **to have other fish to fry**-to have more important deals; **to throw dust into somebody's eyes**-to fool by fine words; **to burn one's fingers**-to harm oneself, to suffer consequences of one's actions; **to throw mud at somebody**-insult or discredit someone, to put a spoke in somebody's wheel-to make it difficult for someone to achieve something they had planned to do.

Phraseological unities approach with phraseological unions with the figurativeness a little. But unlike phraseological unions where the figurative contents reveals only diachronically, in phraseological unities figurativeness, a transformation is realized from the point of view of the modern language. For understanding phraseological unity it is necessary to perceive its components in figurative sense. For example, sense of expression of "make a mountain out of a molehill"-to exaggerate something strongly, reveals only if the word molehill to consider in value "something insignificant, small", and the word mountain-"something very big". As a part of phraseological units there are no the words not clear from the point of view of the modern language.

Phraseological combinations are steady turns which part words both with free, and with phraseologically connected value are: a bosom friend-someone you can be very close with and confide everything in; (to have) of a narrow escape-a situation in which an accident or other unfortunate incident is only just avoided (to escape by miracle); Adam's apple-also known as the laryngeal prominence-is the cartilage that wraps around the front of your larynx-or voice box. The name itself possibly come from the story of Adam and Eve in the Bible-where Adam ate an apple, the forbidden fruit, which became lodged in his throat; Sisyphian labor-In Greek mythology, Sisyphus (or Sisyphos) was the founder and king of Ephyra (now known as Corinth). Hades (in ancient Greek religion and mythology he was the god of the dead and king of the underworld) punished him for cheating death twice by forcing him to roll back down every time it neared the top, repeating this action for eternity. Through the classical influence on modern culture, tasks that are both laborious and futile are therefore described as Sisyphian labor; rack one's brains -to puzzle; to pay attention to somebody-to watch, to listen to, or think about something or someone carefully or with interest. Unlike the phraseological

unions and unities possessing complete indecomposable value, phraseological combinations are characterized by semantic decomposability. In this regard they approach with free phrases.

Phraseological expressions are such steady turns in the structure and the use, which consist of words with free nominative value and semantic. The reproducibility is their only feature: they are used as ready speech units with constant lexical structure and certain semantics.

Phraseological expressions are only turns with literal value of components. Include numerous English proverbs and sayings which are used in a direct sense in structure of phraseological expressions, also they don't make figurative allegorical sense: **live and learn**-live for a century, study for a century; **better untaught than ill taught**-is better to be uneducated, than incorrectly scientific; **many men ,many mind**-how many the heads, is so much and minds; easy said than done-it is easier to tell, than to make; **nothing is impossible to a willing heart**-who wants, that will achieve.

Phrases and sentences in speech form from words. Expressing a thought, we grouped words in its sole discretion, albeit over-dependence on grammatical laws specific language, terms statements and their own language skills. However, if you look closely at the language, it is easy to find pretty considerably a great number of word groups that have become resistant formulas and are used by native speakers in a predetermined form and without any changes. These are phraseological momentum. Such deposits are not formed, is not composed of words during speech, and used to be in finished form, like the blocks in construction.

Phraseological unities are partially non-motivated as their meaning can usually be perceived through the metaphoric meaning of the whole phraseological unit. For example, **to show one's teeth, to wash one's dirty linen in public** if interpreted as semantically motivated through the combined lexical meaning of the component words naturally lead one to understand these in their literal meaning. The metaphoric meaning of the whole unit, however, readily suggests "**take a threatening tone**" or "**show an intention to injure**" for show one's teeth and discuss or make public one's quarrels' for wash one's dirty linen in public. Phraseological units are as a rule marked by a comparatively high degree of stability of the lexical components.

To conclude, it can be said that, by taking into consideration the degree of idiomacity phraseological units are classified into three groups, They are differentiated according to their idiomacity and they are proven with the examples.

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